

DETERMINANTS OF THE BALANCE OF PAYMENTS (BOP) IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the determinants of Nigeria's Balance of Payments (BOP) over the period from 1995 to 2024, focusing on key macroeconomic variables such as Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), exchange rates, inflation, oil prices, and interest rates. Using secondary data from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Bulletin and the World Bank Development Indicators (WDI), the study employs the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to analyze both short-term and long-term relationships. The findings reveal that FDI and oil prices positively influence Nigeria's financial account, while exchange rate volatility, inflation, and interest rates have a negative impact on the current account. The study also highlights that while FDI inflows significantly improve the BOP in the short run, their effect diminishes over time, indicating a short-term rather than long-term solution to BOP imbalances. Exchange rate policies, particularly in the lag period, were found to positively affect the BOP, while inflation and interest rates undermine Nigeria's external balance. The results suggest that Nigeria's over-reliance on oil exports exposes the country to global price fluctuations, reinforcing the need for economic diversification. Based on these findings, the study recommends macroeconomic stabilization and the promotion of non-oil sectors to enhance Nigeria's external sector resilience and reduce vulnerabilities to external shocks.

Keywords: Balance of Payments, Foreign Direct Investment, Exchange Rates, Inflation, Oil Prices, Nigeria, ARDL Model, Economic Diversification

1. INTRODUCTION

The Balance of Payments (BOP) is a fundamental macroeconomic indicator that reflects a country's economic transactions with the rest of the world and serves as a key measure of external sector stability. A sustainable BOP position enhances a country's capacity to meet its international financial obligations, maintain adequate foreign exchange reserves, stabilize the domestic currency, and support long-term economic growth (IMF, 2023; World Bank, 2024). Conversely, persistent BOP deficits are often associated with exchange rate depreciation, rising inflation, depletion of foreign reserves, and increased external vulnerability (Krugman et al., 2022).

In Nigeria, concerns about BOP sustainability have intensified in recent years due to the country's heavy dependence on crude oil exports. Oil exports account for over 80 percent of Nigeria's export earnings and more than half of government revenue, making the external sector highly vulnerable to global oil price fluctuations (CBN, 2024; OPEC, 2023). For instance, the collapse in oil prices during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, followed by sharp price volatility between 2021 and 2024, significantly weakened Nigeria's current account balance and foreign reserve position (World Bank, 2024; Adelegan & Abraham, 2022). Despite episodes of oil price recovery, Nigeria's BOP position has remained fragile, reflecting structural weaknesses in export diversification and external financing.

Recent macroeconomic developments have further complicated Nigeria's BOP dynamics. The persistent depreciation of the naira, particularly following exchange rate liberalization reforms between 2023 and 2024, has increased the cost of imports and external debt servicing, thereby exerting additional pressure on the current account (CBN, 2024; Nwachukwu, 2021). Inflationary pressures driven by exchange rate pass-through effects, energy price shocks, and supply-side constraints have also undermined external competitiveness and investor confidence (Bernard et al., 2024; IMF, 2023). These stylized facts suggest that Nigeria's BOP challenges extend beyond trade imbalances and are closely linked to broader macroeconomic conditions.

Within this context, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has been identified as a potentially stabilizing component of the BOP, particularly through its impact on the capital and financial account. Unlike short-term capital flows, FDI provides relatively stable, long-term financing that can support foreign reserve accumulation, ease balance of payments pressures, and promote structural transformation (UNCTAD, 2024). However, Nigeria's FDI inflows have remained volatile and, in recent years, relatively weak compared to other emerging economies, reflecting concerns about macroeconomic instability, exchange rate uncertainty, and policy inconsistency (Uguru, 2025; Adewole et al., 2025). Between 2019 and 2024, Nigeria experienced a decline in net FDI inflows, coinciding with heightened exchange rate volatility and rising inflation, raising questions about the effectiveness of FDI in stabilizing the BOP. Empirical studies on Nigeria's balance of payments have largely concentrated on trade balance dynamics, exchange rate movements, and external debt sustainability (Ojonugwa et al., 2024; Nwachukwu, 2021). While some recent studies emphasize the sensitivity of the current account to exchange rate volatility (George Anokwuru & Chioma, 2024), relatively limited attention has been given to the role of FDI and its interaction with key macroeconomic variables such as inflation and interest rates in shaping Nigeria's overall BOP position. This gap in the literature is particularly important given Nigeria's ongoing efforts to attract foreign capital and diversify its external revenue base away from crude oil dependence.

Against this backdrop, this study examines the determinants of the balance of payments in Nigeria, with specific emphasis on the roles of Foreign Direct Investment, exchange rates, inflation, and interest rates. The study employs the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) framework and the Error Correction Model (ECM) to capture both the short-run and long-run relationships among these variables. By providing updated empirical evidence, this research contributes to the existing literature and offers policy-relevant insights into how Nigeria can strengthen its external sector stability and reduce vulnerability to external shocks.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews the theoretical and empirical literature on the determinants of the balance of payments. Section 3 presents the methodological framework and model specification. Section 4 discusses the empirical results, while Section 5 concludes the study and provides policy recommendations.

2, LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

This study is anchored on two major theoretical frameworks that are most relevant to explaining the determinants of the balance of payments (BOP) in Nigeria, given the country's macroeconomic structure and external sector characteristics. These are the Mundell–Fleming Model and the Dutch Disease Theory. The selection of these theories is informed by their direct relevance to exchange rate dynamics, capital flows, foreign direct investment (FDI), oil dependence, and balance of payments performance, which constitute the core focus of this study.

2.1.1 The Mundell–Fleming Model

The Mundell–Fleming model, developed by Robert Mundell and Marcus Fleming in the early 1960s, provides a foundational framework for analyzing the interaction between monetary policy, exchange rates, interest rates, and capital flows in an open economy. The model posits that balance of payments equilibrium is influenced by the degree of capital mobility and the prevailing exchange rate regime. Under a flexible exchange rate system, exchange rate adjustments play a central role in correcting external imbalances, while in a fixed exchange rate system, monetary policy and foreign reserve movements are used to stabilize the balance of payments.

The relevance of the Mundell–Fleming model to Nigeria lies in its emphasis on exchange rate volatility, interest rate movements, and foreign capital flows, particularly FDI. Empirical evidence suggests that exchange rate instability in Nigeria has significantly influenced capital inflows and external sector performance. Adelegan and Abraham (2022) find that exchange rate policies in Nigeria directly affect the financial and capital accounts of the balance of payments by shaping foreign investors' expectations. Similarly, Ojonugwa et al. (2024) argue that exchange rate management remains a critical tool for influencing trade balance and capital flows in Nigeria.

However, the applicability of the Mundell–Fleming model to the Nigerian economy has certain limitations. One major criticism is the assumption of perfect or near-perfect capital mobility, which may not hold in developing economies characterized by policy uncertainty, institutional weaknesses, and exposure to external shocks. Uguru (2025) contends that capital flows into Nigeria are often constrained by regulatory controls and macroeconomic instability, thereby limiting the effectiveness of monetary policy in stabilizing the balance of payments. Nwachukwu (2021) further notes that frequent policy reversals and managed exchange rate practices weaken the stabilizing mechanism predicted by the model.

Despite these limitations, the Mundell–Fleming model remains highly relevant to this study, as it provides a theoretical basis for examining how exchange rate movements, interest rates, and FDI jointly influence Nigeria's balance of payments. The model supports the inclusion of key macroeconomic variables in the empirical analysis and aids in interpreting both short-run and long-run dynamics of Nigeria's external sector.

2.1.2 The Dutch Disease Theory

The Dutch Disease theory explains how heavy dependence on natural resource exports can generate structural distortions in an economy and adversely affect balance of payments performance. The theory posits that resource booms such as oil exports lead to real exchange rate appreciation, which reduces the competitiveness of non-resource sectors, particularly manufacturing and agriculture. As these sectors decline, export diversification weakens, imports increase, and the current account deteriorates, thereby destabilizing the balance of payments.

Nigeria represents a classic case for the application of the Dutch Disease theory. The country's strong dependence on crude oil exports has exposed it to recurrent external shocks arising from global oil price volatility. Empirical studies show that oil-driven foreign exchange inflows often lead to currency appreciation, which undermines the competitiveness of non-oil exports and contributes to persistent trade imbalances (Ojonugwa et al., 2024). This structural weakness has been a major factor behind Nigeria's recurring balance of payments challenges. Nevertheless, the Dutch Disease theory has been criticized for its deterministic outlook. Critics argue that resource dependence does not inevitably lead to balance of payments instability if appropriate macroeconomic and structural policies are implemented. George Anokwuru and Chioma (2024) emphasize that effective exchange rate management, investment in infrastructure, and economic diversification can mitigate the adverse effects of resource booms. Adewole et al. (2025) further argue that global market conditions and domestic policy choices

play a crucial role in shaping balance of payments outcomes, beyond resource dependence alone.

In the context of this study, the Dutch Disease theory is relevant for explaining the structural sources of Nigeria's balance of payments imbalances. It provides a framework for understanding how oil price fluctuations, exchange rate appreciation, and limited export diversification interact to affect the trade balance and overall external stability. When combined with the Mundell–Fleming model, the theory offers a comprehensive explanation of both the short-run macroeconomic and long-run structural determinants of Nigeria's balance of payments.

2.2 Empirical Literature

A substantial body of empirical literature identifies exchange rate movements as a key determinant of Nigeria's balance of payments. Using cointegration techniques, Ojonugwa et al. (2024) find that exchange rate fluctuations significantly influence Nigeria's trade balance, with currency depreciation improving export competitiveness, particularly in the non-oil sector. However, the study also emphasizes that oil price volatility remains the dominant driver of Nigeria's external balance, limiting the effectiveness of exchange rate adjustments.

Similarly, Uguru (2025) demonstrates that although exchange rate devaluation can improve trade balances in the short run, its long-term effectiveness in Nigeria is constrained by the inelastic demand for crude oil exports. This finding aligns with the Mundell–Fleming framework, which highlights the importance of capital mobility and exchange rate regimes, but also exposes its limitations in resource-dependent economies such as Nigeria. Also, Shobande (2018) documents that exchange-rate policy is relevant for industrial outcomes using cointegration evidence, implying that external competitiveness can be influenced through exchange rate related policy channels that ultimately shape trade and BOP performance. Complementarily, Andohol (2020) evaluates J-curve dynamics for Nigeria (1970–2018) and shows that structural breaks (e.g., policy regime shifts) can alter the adjustment path of the trade balance following exchange-rate movements, an important caution for interpreting exchange-rate effects on external balances without accounting for breaks

Several studies emphasize the role of FDI as a stabilizing component of the balance of payments, particularly through the financial account. Adelegan and Abraham (2022), using an Error Correction Model, find that FDI inflows exert a positive short-run effect on Nigeria's financial account, thereby contributing to BOP stabilization. However, they caution that the long-run impact of FDI remains uncertain due to exchange rate volatility and oil price fluctuations.

Bernard et al. (2024) support this finding, noting that FDI can alleviate BOP deficits when inflows are diversified across productive sectors of the economy. In contrast, when FDI is concentrated in the oil sector, its stabilizing impact on the BOP is often short-lived. Mugo et al. (2023) further argue that FDI plays a critical role in financing Nigeria's current account deficits, especially in the presence of low domestic savings. These findings underscore the importance of the composition and sustainability of FDI inflows in determining Nigeria's external balance. Mobosi and Madueme (2016) find that macroeconomic uncertainty particularly exchange-rate variability and inflation-related uncertainty reduces foreign investment inflows (FDI/FPI), implying that weak macro fundamentals can constrain the capital/financial account's ability to offset current-account pressures. Relatedly, Meme and Madueme (2016) emphasize reserve adequacy and external-sector management concerns, supporting the policy view that BOP sustainability requires buffers and credible macroeconomic management. Evidence by Olowe (2022) associates FDI with capital formation (while noting adverse roles for exchange rate and inflation on private investment), suggesting that the BOP-supporting role of capital inflows depends on domestic macro stability and the investment channel

Oil price volatility has been consistently identified as a major source of BOP instability in Nigeria, reflecting the country's heavy dependence on crude oil exports. Adekunle et al. (2025), applying the ARDL bounds testing approach, find that oil prices significantly influence Nigeria's balance of payments through both the trade and financial accounts. Their results indicate that increases in oil prices improve external balances, while price declines exacerbate BOP deficits.

Pamogho et al. (2023) similarly observe that positive oil price shocks strengthen Nigeria's financial account, whereas negative shocks deteriorate the trade balance. Ullah and Nobanee (2025) extend this analysis to oil-dependent economies and conclude that oil price volatility affects the BOP through exchange rate adjustments and current account fluctuations. These findings strongly support the Dutch Disease theory, which explains how resource dependence exposes economies to persistent external sector vulnerabilities. Nigeria's external balance remains highly exposed to oil-market conditions. Using descriptive evidence, Emediegwu and Okeke (2017) show that oil dependency and oil-price volatility are closely linked with unstable macro outcomes, reinforcing the view that external accounts are structurally fragile in oil-led phases. Also, Longe, Adelokun, and Omitogun (2018) apply ARDL (1977–2015) and report that oil-price fluctuations are a significant long-run driver of Nigeria's current account, implying that persistent oil shocks transmit directly into external-balance outcomes

Other empirical studies focus on the roles of inflation and trade openness in influencing Nigeria's balance of payments. Elakkad and Hussein (2023) find that inflation and exchange rate misalignment significantly undermine trade balance and current account stability in Nigeria. Ahmed (2024) further demonstrates that although exchange rate devaluation may yield short-run trade gains, inflationary pressures often offset these benefits in the long run, worsening the BOP position.

The effect of trade openness on Nigeria's balance of payments remains mixed. Adewole et al. (2025) argue that trade openness enhances export competitiveness and supports current account stability. However, they also acknowledge that Nigeria's reliance on oil exports and limited export diversification reduce the effectiveness of trade liberalization in improving the BOP. Nguyen et al. (2023) similarly caution that the benefits of trade openness may be offset by inflationary pressures and increased import demand.

Although existing empirical studies provide valuable insights into the individual effects of exchange rates, FDI, oil prices, inflation, and trade openness on Nigeria's balance of payments, several gaps remain. Most studies focus on isolated relationships rather than examining the combined and interactive effects of these variables on the BOP. Moreover, limited attention has been given to the long-run sustainability of FDI inflows and how structural factors, such as oil dependence and exchange rate volatility, constrain the effectiveness of macroeconomic policies.

This study seeks to fill these gaps by jointly examining the effects of FDI, exchange rates, inflation, and oil prices on Nigeria's balance of payments using advanced econometric techniques, including the ARDL and ECM frameworks. By integrating both short-run and long-run dynamics, the study provides a more comprehensive understanding of Nigeria's external sector performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical Framework

This study adopts the Mundell–Fleming model as its theoretical framework, given its relevance in explaining balance of payments dynamics in an open economy. The model posits that exchange rates, interest rates, and capital flows jointly determine external balance under varying degrees of capital mobility. In the Nigerian context, exchange rate movements and interest rate differentials influence foreign direct investment inflows and capital movements,

which in turn affect the balance of payments. Drawing from this framework, the study models the balance of payments as a function of foreign direct investment, exchange rate, inflation, and interest rate. The framework provides the theoretical basis for the ARDL and ECM approaches used to estimate both short-run and long-run relationships among the variables.

3.2 Model Specification

The study applied an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to assess both the short-term and long-term dynamics between the selected variables and Nigeria’s BOP. The ARDL model was preferred because it could capture the dynamic relationships among variables, even when they were integrated at different levels (i.e., I(0) and I(1)). The ARDL approach was ideal for time series data as it allowed the study to assess both short-term fluctuations and long-term trends simultaneously.

The model was specified as follows:

$$BOP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FDI_t + \beta_2 EXR_t + \beta_3 INF_t + \beta_4 OIL_t + \beta_5 IR_t + \epsilon_t \dots \dots \dots \text{equ 1}$$

Where

BOP_t = Balance of Payments at time t

FDI_t = Foreign Direct Investment at time t

EXR_t = the exchange rate at time t

INF_t = inflation at time t

OIL_t = oil prices at time t

IR_t = interest rates at time t

ε_t = error term.

3.3 Variables, Measures, and Descriptions in Tabular Format

The table below summarizes the variables used in the study, their measurements, and expected signs based on theoretical expectations:

Table 1: Variables Measurement and Description

Variable	Measurement	Description	Expected Sign
Balance of Payments (BOP)	Current Account Balance / Total Financial Account	Net financial transactions between Nigeria and the rest of the world.	Dependent variable (No sign)
FDI (Foreign Direct Investment)	Annual FDI inflows (USD)	Foreign investments in Nigeria’s productive sectors.	Positive (+)
Exchange Rate (EXR)	Official exchange rate (NGN/USD)	The market price at which the Nigerian Naira is exchanged for foreign currencies.	Negative (-)
Inflation (INF)	Consumer Price Index (CPI)	The rate at which the general level of prices for goods and services is rising.	Negative (-)
Oil Prices (OIL)	Crude oil prices (USD/barrel)	Average global price of crude oil, a key driver of Nigeria’s trade balance.	Positive (+)
Interest Rates (IR)	Lending rate (%)	The rate at which financial institutions lend money to borrowers in Nigeria.	Negative (-)

Source: Researchers idea (2025)

3.4 Type and Source of Data

The study utilized secondary data sourced from reliable and reputable institutions such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Bulletin and the World Bank Development Indicators (WDI) database. The data covered the period from 1995 to 2024. This period was chosen due to Nigeria's significant economic reforms, including political transitions, trade liberalization, and

financial sector deregulation. This timeframe provides ample data to examine how these reforms, alongside global economic shifts, influenced the key determinants of the country's Balance of Payments (BOP) trends and dynamics. Secondary data was chosen for its consistency, reliability, and extensive historical records, which made it suitable for assessing long-term trends and examining the relationship between Nigeria's BOP and macroeconomic variables. The data included key variables such as FDI, exchange rates, inflation, oil prices, and interest rates, which were essential for understanding the dynamics of the BOP. The choice of data from trusted sources ensured the quality and credibility of the study's analysis, making it suitable for economic policy recommendations.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

The data analysis followed a structured procedure to ensure the validity and robustness of the empirical results. Descriptive statistics were first employed to summarize the basic characteristics of the data, including measures of central tendency and dispersion. This step provided preliminary insights into the behavior and distribution of the variables and helped identify potential outliers. Subsequently, the Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) unit root test was applied to examine the stationarity properties of the series. Stationarity testing is essential in time-series analysis to prevent spurious regression results and to determine the appropriate econometric technique. Variables found to be non-stationary at level were differenced accordingly.

Given that the variables exhibited mixed orders of integration, the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach was adopted to examine both the short-run and long-run relationships between balance of payments and its determinants. The ARDL framework is appropriate because it accommodates variables integrated of different orders and provides efficient estimates in small samples. To validate the reliability of the estimated model, several post-estimation diagnostic tests were conducted. These include the Breusch–Pagan test for heteroscedasticity, the Ramsey RESET test for model specification, the Jarque–Bera test for residual normality, and the CUSUM test to assess parameter stability over time. Together, these diagnostics confirm the robustness and consistency of the model estimates.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 2: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

	BOP	FDI	EXR	INF	OILP	IR
Mean	4.174	4445.383	143.632	19.235	51.318	18.084
Median	4.196	1509.416	125.810	12.880	40.950	17.585
Maximum	15.329	38219.850	746.890	72.840	116.909	29.800
Minimum	-2.035	298.614	0.890	5.390	14.140	9.250
Std. Dev.	3.768	7481.416	153.678	16.993	34.999	4.153
Skewness	0.515	3.130	1.849	1.797	0.673	0.518
Kurtosis	3.577	13.638	7.348	5.038	2.063	4.122
Jarque-Bera	2.263	215.836	52.944	27.748	4.366	3.601
Probability	0.323	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.113	0.165

Source: Authors' Computation (2025)

Table 2 gives a very informative depiction of the variables that determine the Balance of Payments (BOP) in Nigeria. The average of the BOP is not very low or high at 4.174 and it means that the overall external transactions of the country have mostly been even over the period of study albeit with variations. The lowest and highest values of the BOP are -2.035 and 15.329 which indicates that Nigeria has had both deficits and surpluses. This is also reflected in the standard deviation of 3.768 which shows volatility in the external sector in Nigeria. The value of the skewness at 0.515 shows that the distribution of the BOP is a little skewed to the

right, that is, although there are some instances when the balance is negative, most of the observations will be BOP-favourable.

In the case of the explanatory variables, FDI has a mean of 4445.383 indicating high inflows of foreign investment to Nigeria. The standard deviation is however high at 7481.416 indicating that there is a high degree of variability in the levels of FDI which can be explained by external sources like the global economic environment and fluidity of the investment climate in Nigeria. Even the exchange rate (EXR) whose mean is 143.632 is characterized by a high level of fluctuation as indicated by its maximum of 746.890 and minimum of 0.890 indicating extreme volatility of the value of the Naira with the US dollar. The skew of 1.849 and kurtosis value of 7.348 indicate that the exchange rate distribution is extremely skewed with some sharp depreciation periods. This is in line with the fact that the country is dependent on oil revenues which can exert a significant pressure on the foreign exchange market.

Concerning other variables, inflation (INF) has a mean of 19.235 and a maximum of 72.840, which means that there have been inflationary pressures in Nigeria during the period of study. The oil price (OILP) which has a mean value of 51.318 and a maximum of 116.909 is used to show the volatility in the global oil markets and how important oil revenues have become to the external account of Nigeria. To some extent, the interest rate (IR) of 18.084 is not as unstable as other variables are, yet its standard deviation of 4.153 indicates that the cost of borrowing remains to vary as well. As seen in Jarque Berra tests, the majority of the variables, especially FDI, EXR, and INF do not accept the null hypothesis of normality (p-values of 0.000), which indicates that they are not normally distributed and as such, their relationship with the BOP may be non-linear. The non-normality of these variables may also have effect on the type of econometric model to be adopted as it may need to adopt a method that is able to deal with skewed or non-normal data distribution like the ARDL model that has been adopted in the study.

Table 3: Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit root Stationarity Test

Variables	Test at Levels			Test at 1 st difference			Inference
	ADF statistic	t-statistic	Prob.*	ADF statistic	t-statistic	Prob.*	
BOP	-1.192624	-2.967767	0.6638	-7.321054	-2.97185	0.0003	I(1)
FDI	-1.87474	-2.96397	0.3391	-4.91027	-2.97185	0.0005	I(1)
EXR	-5.25859	-2.96777	0.0002	-7.564865	-2.98103	0.0001	I(0)
INF	-3.75325	-2.96777	0.0026	-5.456753	-2.98103	0.0011	I(0)
OIL	-4.57498	-2.96397	0.0010	-5.93727	-2.97185	0.0002	I(0)
IR	-1.291616	-2.96397	0.6202	-6.43296	-2.96777	0.0003	I(1)

Source: Researcher’ Computations (2025)

The results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test presented in Table 3 reveal the stationarity properties of the variables under study. For the Balance of Payments (BOP), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), and Interest Rates (IR), the test statistics at levels fail to reject the null hypothesis of a unit root, as the probability values are higher than 0.05. However, when tested at the first difference, these variables become stationary, with p-values of 0.0003, 0.0005, and 0.0003, respectively, indicating that they are I(1), or integrated of order one. In contrast, the Exchange Rate (EXR), Inflation (INF), and Oil Prices (OIL) are stationary at levels, as their ADF statistics are significant at the 1% level (p-values of 0.0002, 0.0011, and 0.0002), meaning these variables are I(0), integrated of order zero. These results suggest that the study can proceed with the ARDL model, as it can handle variables integrated at different orders (I(0) and I(1)), ensuring the robustness of the econometric analysis

Table 4: Bounds Test

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	4.450	10%	1.92	2.89
K	4	5%	2.17	3.21
		2.5%	2.43	3.51
		1%	2.73	3.9

Source: Researcher’ Computations (2025)

The results presented in Table 4 show the findings of the F-Bounds Test for cointegration, which assesses the existence of a long-term relationship among the variables in the ARDL model. The F-statistic of 4.450 exceeds the critical values at all significance levels, indicating the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no long-term relationship among the variables. Specifically, the F-statistic surpasses the critical values at the 10%, 5%, 2.5%, and 1% levels, suggesting the presence of a cointegrating relationship between the variables. This result supports the use of the ARDL model for further analysis, confirming that the selected variables (such as FDI, exchange rates, oil prices, inflation, and interest rates) are related in the long run.

Table 5: ARDL Error Correction Regression

ARDL Error Correction Regression				
Dependent Variable: D(LBOP)				
ECM Regression				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LBOP(-1))	0.293	0.140	2.090	0.047
D(LFD1)	1.141	0.301	3.788	0.002
D(LFD1(-1))	-0.134	0.330	-0.405	0.692
D(LEXR)	-0.383	0.555	-0.690	0.502
D(LEXR(-1))	2.085	0.529	3.939	0.002
D(LINF)	-0.870	0.223	-3.907	0.002
D(OLP)	0.594	0.209	2.839	0.014
D(LIR)	-0.890	0.283	-3.144	0.008
CointEq(-1)*	-0.658	0.167	-3.931	0.002
R-squared	0.831	Mean dependent var		0.056
Adjusted R-squared	0.751	S.D. dependent var		0.416
Log likelihood	11.656	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.126
Durbin-Watson stat	2.638			

Source: Authors’ Computation (2025)

The results reported in Table 5 present the ARDL Error Correction Model (ECM) estimates with the change in the balance of payments as the dependent variable. The coefficient of the error correction term (ECT) is -0.658 and statistically significant at the 1% level. This negative and significant coefficient confirms the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables. Economically, the magnitude of the coefficient implies that approximately 66% of any short-run disequilibrium in Nigeria’s balance of payments is corrected within one period, indicating a relatively fast speed of adjustment toward long-run equilibrium. This suggests that although Nigeria’s external sector is frequently exposed to shocks, corrective mechanisms—through exchange rate adjustments, capital flows, and trade responses—operate reasonably quickly to restore equilibrium.

With respect to foreign direct investment, the contemporaneous coefficient of FDI is positive and statistically significant, indicating that increases in FDI inflows lead to an immediate

improvement in the balance of payments. Specifically, a 1% increase in FDI inflows improves the BOP by approximately 1.14% in the short run, reflecting the role of FDI as a stable source of foreign capital that strengthens the financial account. However, the lagged FDI term is statistically insignificant, suggesting that the impact of FDI on Nigeria’s BOP is largely short-lived rather than persistent. This distinction between short-run and long-run effects is empirically grounded in the lag structure of the ARDL model and implies that unless FDI inflows are sustained and diversified into productive sectors, their long-term stabilizing effect on the BOP may be limited.

The exchange rate exhibits a mixed effect on the balance of payments. While the contemporaneous exchange rate coefficient is negative but insignificant, the lagged exchange rate term is positive and statistically significant. This pattern suggests that exchange rate changes do not immediately translate into BOP adjustments, but their effects materialize with a lag, likely through delayed responses in export volumes, import substitution, and contract adjustments. This result is consistent with theoretical expectations and empirical evidence that exchange rate effects on trade and external balances are not instantaneous, especially in economies like Nigeria where oil exports dominate and non-oil export responsiveness is weak. Inflation exerts a negative and statistically significant effect on the balance of payments. A 1% increase in inflation worsens the BOP by approximately 0.87%, reflecting the erosion of external competitiveness caused by rising domestic prices. High inflation increases production costs, discourages exports, and stimulates import demand, thereby exerting pressure on the current account. Similarly, the interest rate coefficient is negative and significant, implying that higher domestic interest rates deter foreign investment and increase the cost of capital, thereby weakening capital inflows and the financial account. These findings highlight the importance of macroeconomic stability as a prerequisite for external sector sustainability.

Oil prices display a positive and significant relationship with the balance of payments. Quantitatively, a 1% increase in oil prices improves the BOP by about 0.59%, underscoring Nigeria’s continued dependence on crude oil exports as the primary source of foreign exchange earnings. While this result confirms the revenue-enhancing effect of oil price increases on the BOP, it also exposes Nigeria’s vulnerability to external commodity price shocks, reinforcing the structural concerns emphasized by the Dutch Disease theory.

Overall, the model exhibits strong explanatory power, with an R-squared of 0.831 and an adjusted R-squared of 0.751, indicating that the selected macroeconomic variables explain a substantial proportion of variations in Nigeria’s balance of payments. The Durbin–Watson statistic suggests the absence of serial correlation, lending further credibility to the estimates. Thus, the findings reveal that FDI and oil prices positively influence Nigeria’s balance of payments, while inflation and interest rates exert destabilizing effects. Exchange rate impacts are largely lagged rather than contemporaneous, reflecting delayed adjustment mechanisms. The significant and sizeable error correction term confirms rapid convergence to long-run equilibrium, but the results also emphasize the need for policies that promote sustained FDI inflows, macroeconomic stability, and export diversification to reduce Nigeria’s vulnerability to external shocks.

Table 5: Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.177322	Prob. F(23,1)	0.9737
Obs*R-squared	20.07720	Prob. Chi-Square(23)	0.6373
Scaled explained SS	1.037055	Prob. Chi-Square(23)	1.0000

Source: Authors’ Computation (2025)

The results from the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test (Table 6) show no evidence of heteroscedasticity in the model. The F-statistic of 0.177322 (p-value = 0.9737) and the Obs*R-squared value of 20.07720 (p-value = 0.6373) both indicate that the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity (constant variance of residuals) cannot be rejected. Additionally, the Scaled explained SS statistic (p-value = 1.0000) further supports this conclusion. These results confirm that the model’s residuals exhibit constant variance, ensuring the reliability of the estimates.

Cusum Test

The Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) test, displayed in the figure above, is used to evaluate the structural stability of the ARDL model over the sample period. The null hypothesis of the CUSUM test asserts that the model is stable and that its parameters do not vary systematically over time. In the graph, the blue CUSUM line remains entirely within the 5% significance boundaries (represented by the red dashed lines), indicating no structural break in the regression coefficients during the estimation period. This outcome suggests that the model’s parameters are stable and that the relationship between inflation and the explanatory variables remains consistent over time. Thus, the ARDL model passes this crucial diagnostic test, enhancing confidence in the robustness of the long-run and short-run estimates derived from the model.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study provide important insights into the macroeconomic determinants of Nigeria’s balance of payments (BOP) and their transmission mechanisms. The results indicate that foreign direct investment (FDI) exerts a positive and statistically significant effect on the BOP in the short run, suggesting that inflows of foreign capital contribute to improving the financial account and easing external financing constraints. Economically, this implies that FDI serves as an immediate source of foreign exchange that supports external balance. Similar short-run effects of FDI on external balance have been documented in Nigeria and other developing economies where capital inflows temporarily offset current account pressures (Adelegan & Abraham, 2022; Bernard et al., 2024). However, the insignificance of the lagged FDI term suggests that these gains are not persistent, indicating that FDI alone may not guarantee long-term BOP stability unless it is sustained and directed toward productive, export-oriented sectors.

The exchange rate results reveal that contemporaneous exchange rate changes do not significantly affect the BOP, while lagged exchange rate movements exert a positive and significant impact. This pattern suggests that exchange rate adjustments influence external balance with a delay, reflecting sluggish responses of exports and imports to price changes. This outcome is consistent with theoretical expectations and empirical evidence for Nigeria,

where trade contracts, import dependence, and the dominance of oil exports limit immediate adjustment to exchange rate movements (Nwachukwu, 2021; Ojonugwa et al., 2024). The finding also aligns with the Mundell–Fleming framework, which predicts delayed external-sector responses under imperfect capital mobility and structural rigidities.

Inflation is found to have a negative and significant effect on the BOP, indicating that rising domestic prices undermine international competitiveness by increasing production costs and reducing export performance. From an economic standpoint, persistent inflation erodes the price advantage of domestic goods, stimulates import demand, and worsens the current account. This finding corroborates evidence from Nigeria and other emerging economies where macroeconomic instability constrains external-sector performance (Adewole et al., 2025; Ahmed, 2024). Similarly, interest rates exert a negative and significant effect on the BOP, suggesting that higher borrowing costs discourage investment and capital inflows while increasing debt-service burdens. In developing economies, elevated interest rates may therefore weaken the financial account rather than attract sustainable foreign capital.

Oil prices exhibit a positive and statistically significant relationship with the BOP, underscoring Nigeria’s continued dependence on crude oil exports as the primary source of foreign exchange earnings. Economically, this implies that improvements in Nigeria’s BOP are largely driven by favorable external oil market conditions rather than domestic structural strength. While this result is consistent with evidence from oil-exporting economies where higher oil prices boost export revenues and external balances (Pamogho et al., 2023), it also highlights Nigeria’s vulnerability to external shocks. Dependence on oil revenues exposes the BOP to sharp reversals during periods of global oil price decline, reinforcing concerns raised by the Dutch Disease theory.

Therefore, the findings suggest that Nigeria’s BOP dynamics are shaped by short-run capital inflows, delayed exchange rate effects, macroeconomic stability conditions, and oil price movements. Although several variables are statistically significant, their economic impact is conditional on structural factors such as export diversification, inflation control, and effective allocation of foreign capital. This implies that sustainable improvement in Nigeria’s external balance requires not only appropriate macroeconomic policies but also long-term structural reforms aimed at reducing oil dependence and strengthening the productive base of the economy.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the determinants of Nigeria’s balance of payments (BOP), focusing on the roles of foreign direct investment (FDI), exchange rates, inflation, oil prices, and interest rates using the ARDL framework over the period 1995–2024. The findings reveal that FDI inflows and oil price increases improve Nigeria’s BOP, while exchange rate volatility, inflation, and high interest rates exert destabilizing effects. These results underscore the structural vulnerability of Nigeria’s external sector and the continued dominance of crude oil exports in driving external balance outcomes.

In light of these findings, several policy recommendations are proposed. First, the Federal Government of Nigeria, through the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (FMITI) and the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC), should intensify efforts to attract and retain FDI into non-oil, export-oriented sectors such as manufacturing, agro-processing, and technology. This will help ensure that FDI inflows generate sustainable foreign exchange earnings rather than short-term capital inflows.

Second, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should prioritize macroeconomic stability by implementing monetary policies aimed at controlling inflation and reducing excessive exchange rate volatility. Stable inflation and exchange rate conditions are critical for improving export competitiveness and encouraging long-term foreign investment. In addition, the CBN

should adopt interest rate policies that balance inflation control with the need to stimulate productive investment, thereby strengthening the financial account of the BOP.

Third, the Federal Ministry of Finance, Budget and National Planning, in collaboration with relevant sectoral agencies, should accelerate economic diversification policies by supporting non-oil exports through targeted incentives, infrastructure development, and export financing schemes. Reducing Nigeria's reliance on crude oil exports will lessen the economy's exposure to external commodity price shocks and enhance the resilience of the balance of payments.

Finally, strengthening institutional frameworks and policy consistency remains essential. Regulatory agencies responsible for trade, investment, and financial oversight should improve policy coordination and transparency to enhance investor confidence. Such institutional reforms will help Nigeria better absorb external shocks and achieve long-term balance of payments sustainability.

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